

GDI user journeys

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Aim and scope

This document aims to give a high-level description of GDI's most common usages and, through them, provide a broad overview of expected functionalities and basic requirements.

By reading and dissecting each user journey and story, the reader can envision the bricklaying work being done towards a pan-European health data network infrastructure, with real examples of daily research work (ranging from variant search over large populations to supporting cancer multimodal initiatives) where this network will be not only helpful but foundational.

The GDI user journey section describes the specific steps a user will take when interacting with the GDI. It gives a high-level description of GDI's most common usages and, through them, provides a broad overview of expected functionalities and basic requirements. The user journeys map out the user's experience, from the initial point of contact (i.e. the authentication into GDI Federation) to the final goal (i.e. data access and analysis), providing context and a deeper understanding of the considerations and challenges the user faces along the way. These **user journeys** are designed to be technology-agnostic, focusing on user needs rather than specific implementations. Subsequently, **user stories** have been derived from these user journeys, providing practical examples.

Versioning

Date	Mvm	Who	Description
21/06/2024	v1	EGJ (BSC)	First draft, internal discussion
20/07/2024	v2	CHF (BSC)	Second draft after discussion with WP7 - Marco Morelli's team
26/08/2024	v3	CHF (BSC)	Version after discussion within full Pillar III
30/08/2024	v4	LP (BSC)	Include comments by Pillar I + other feedback
20/09/2024	v5	LP (BSC)	Updated numbering of stories, stories names and updated stories content
09/12/2024	v6	CHF (BSC)	Added two new user journeys from D7.5 user stories
20/01/2025	v7	LP, CHF, EGJ (BSC)	Final version of user journeys to be frozen

Glossary

- **(Data) User.** An identified, authenticated real person belonging to a research or health organisation that uses GDI infrastructure. A user has a series of connotations according to their background according to the HealthyCloud user profiles and sub-profiles¹, the 1+MG Governance and ELSI², and the 1+MG Glossary³:
 - **Researchers.** Researchers are those individuals that will interact with GDI's infrastructure with the goal to obtain, process, and/or analyse research data and its potentially associated outcomes.
 - **Healthcare professional.** A healthcare professional is a person that has an active role in processing, analysing and/or understanding health-related data. Their main goal while using GDI's infrastructure is to obtain knowledge that could be transferred to clinical practice.
 - **Policy maker.** It is a person, or group of people, responsible for or involved in formulating policies⁴, especially in politics and related to healthcare. In order to fulfil their duties, they might need to access high level statistics of GDI, usage of GDI's data, or GDI's data in its fraction or completeness. A user also includes consultancies who develop policies for a policy maker.
- **Data provider.** According to the definition in HealthyCloud¹, a data provider is a person or entity that generates and/or makes available health-related data into the 1+MG, either as a product of their activity or as mandated by another individual or organisation. The data provider may not be the one who has collected the data. The data provider does not act vis-a-vis the user but transfers the (legal) responsibility for the disclosure to the user to the Genome EDIC. Then, the 1+MG Governance and ELSI², and the 1+MG Glossary³ requires for extra detail:
 - **Data controller (can be a joint controller).** Data controllers are those that, as a natural or legal person, as well as a public authority, alone or jointly with others, determines the purposes and means of processing GDI's data or a subset of it (for instance the data in a national node). A data controller does not require to have access to the data nor to host it to exercise the role. In addition, a data controller is a qualification under the GDPR and changes along the data life cycle.
 - Data provider are controllers for bringing data into the Genome EDIC
 - The Genome EDIC is controller for the disclosure to the user
 - The user is controller for the data use such as a research project

¹ FAIR Health Data Portal expected users' interactions: <https://zenodo.org/records/10225882>

² 1+MG Governance and ELSI: <https://framework.onemilliongenomes.eu/governance-elsi>

³ 1+MG Glossary - version for 1+MG Framework: <https://zenodo.org/records/8279620>

⁴ Health Researchers and Policy Makers: A Need to Strengthen Relationship: <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC3191660/>

- When we have subject-level data discovery in advance for an access request, the user and EDIC are joint controllers for those operations.
- **Data host.** A natural or legal person, a public authority, or a third party entity (such as Amazon, Microsoft or Google) that stores any subset of GDI's data, usually on behalf of another entity (usually a data controller).
- **IT infrastructure provider.** It is a legal person, as well as public authority, that contributes to GDI by providing physical and/or computational infrastructure to achieve the project's goals in terms of data storage capabilities, data processing capabilities, and/or logistic operative support capabilities to enable meeting the project's long-term needs.
 - **Data processor.** According to the 1+MG Glossary³, a Data processor is a natural or legal person, as well as public authority, which processes personal and/or health data on behalf of the Data controller.
- **(Data) Processing.** Data processing covers any sort of process (including holding data) covering the non exhausting aspects of training AI models, analysis of clinical and/or genetic data for research purposes, identification of shared pathologies across datasets (both using clinical and/or genetic data to do so) or high level or low level statistics on data collections, data sets or individual records.
- **Data.** Any digital information susceptible to being used in health research and regulated by previously mentioned laws and stored within GDI's premises.
 - **(Individual) Record.** Data related to individual data subjects.
 - **Data set.** Individual records that are grouped in a certain context (for example: project that generated the "data", clinical condition definition, etc.). they can be characterised using non-personal metadata.
 - **Data collection.** Data sets that are grouped together in a certain context and coming from the same data controller(s). They can be characterised with non-personal metadata. A data collection, for instance, refers to data of a cohort or public registry.
 - **Clinical data.** Personal data related to the physical or mental health of an individual data subject independent of its origin (e.g. from healthcare, research, clinical trials contexts - among others). In 1+MG's Glossary this is referred to as "health data", with other granularity as "healthcare data" and "health research data"; in other projects "phenotypic data" is also used to describe this information and in Beacon v2 it is called "phenoclinic data".
 - **Genetic data.** Personal data related to the inherited or acquired genetic characteristics of an individual which give unique information about their physiology or health, and which results from an analysis of a biological sample from the individual question.

Workflow

Amend an application

#: ujGdi06	Story name: Application submitted by user is rejected and an amend is request
	Triggered by User Role: Researcher and/or health professional
	Authors and Contributors: EGJ, CHF, LP
Preconditions: <ul style="list-style-type: none">- The user has completed data access request user story (ujGdi04)	
Description: <p>The user is notified, within the accorded deliberation time, through one of the official channels regarding the updated status of his/her petition.</p> <p>With the petition rejection, the committee may ask for the user to amend the petition and include extra information required to come to a decision.</p> <p>The user is then able to complete the petition and, once all the information asked for has been included, resubmit the application by following the user story (ujGdi04)</p>	
Postconditions: <ul style="list-style-type: none">- The user gets access to the requested datasets- The valid access permission is registered in the appropriate infrastructure.	
Needs discussion and clarification: <ul style="list-style-type: none">- None	

Preconditions:

- The user already has been authenticated and requested access to several datasets across several nodes as per usGdi04, and has been approved as per [ujGdi05](#).
- The user has selected an approved workflow that will perform the computation of interest ([ujGdi10](#)).

Description:

A user accesses the Federated Data Computation Dashboard and selects the workflow of interest, as well as the datasets of interest where the workflow will be run. Then, the user provides parameters requested by each task of the analytical workflow using the Federated Computation Dashboard.

The user, from a known organisation, gains access to a national SPE, where data is made available to them (see preconditions). Depending on the project the user is involved in, the user is authorised to certain datasets.

The user chooses among the analysis tools available for them at the SPE. It sets up the run parameters and input files.

The archived datasets are made accessible at the SPE on behalf of the user. In case storage's credentials are not integrated in LS-AAI, the user will provide them to the SPE directly.

The SPE makes the datasets available to the run computing environment, ready to be consumed by the analysis and visualisation tools.

The user obtains the analysis output at its SPE private workspace. Depending on the data type associated with the output, they can (1) be visualised at the SPE using a visualisation tool, (2) further analysed using other analysis tools, (3) be downloaded ([ujGdi09](#)) from the SPE (with previous validation by the SPE data governance officer).

Postconditions:

- Any information private to the user's researcher will not be distributed with any other entity.

Download analytical (and mostly aggregated) results

#: ujGdi09	Story name: Download analytical results
	Triggered by User Role: Researcher and/or health professional
	Authors and Contributors: EGJ, CHF
Preconditions: <ul style="list-style-type: none">- The user has executed an analysis following ujGdi08.- The user has been granted access to the results of the analysis executed (all nodes had vetoed the results).- All nodes can connect the other nodes with the purpose of accessing the results of that user executions they have stored. <p>The analytical workflow the user selected is composed by two sections: 1) a series of tasks that must be run in multiple national nodes to extract key information from the datasets of interest by the researcher, to generate intermediate results (ujGdi08); 2) an extra step that will aggregate the results from the previous step in a single “final result” (ujGdi08).</p> <p>There will be scenarios where the second step is not necessary and what is called “partial final results” are, in fact, the “final results” (one in each of the involved national nodes).</p> <p>To the user, it is key to be able to download both the “partial final results” and the “final result” of the selected analytical workflow in order to pursue their research.</p> <p>The national node the researcher belongs to will be the one in charge to collect the “partial final results”. If the second step (aggregation) is necessary, it will also be responsible to make the aggregation (for example, the meta analysis done from multiple GWAS analysis). Then, both the “partial final results” and the “final result” should be accessible from the user’s node.</p>	
Postconditions: <ul style="list-style-type: none">- Both “partial final results” and “final results” are accessible by the user at the end of ujGdi08 + ujGdi09 (this user journey).- Other nodes involved in ujGdi08 are allowed to delete temporary results after some time of ujGdi08	

Submission of an analytical workflow

#: ujGdi10	Story name: Submission of an analytical workflow
	Triggered by User Role:
	Authors and Contributors: EGJ, CHF
Preconditions <ul style="list-style-type: none">- The user authenticates themselves in GDI following ujGdi01- The user understands GDI's Federated Computation Dashboard features and how to define an analytical workflow.	
Description <p>The user has an idea of an analytical workflow in order to answer their scientific questions, for which they want to use the GDI infrastructure and data resources.</p> <p>In order to do so, the user inspects the Marketplace, where all the applications (software and models) reside. Picking from the list and concatenating the different applications, the user is able to create a new analytical workflow, either using a graphical user interface application such as the Federated Computation Dashboard or using a workflow description language.</p> <p>Once the user has the analytical workflow defined, they can submit it to acceptance into GDI using the same Federated Computation Dashboard. GDI will answer the user in a reasonable amount of time. During this time GDI will: A) check that the analytical workflow does not leak any data nor performs any undesired operation, and B) inform the national nodes about the new workflow, which will have some time (within the original reasonable amount of time) to test the workflow and raise any technical issues in which case they can request changes be made to the workflow and the application to begin anew. If both A and B are successful, ujGdi11. Otherwise ujGdi12.</p>	
Postconditions <ul style="list-style-type: none">- The analytical workflow is submitted into GDI's system and accessible by GDI's staff and national nodes for its validation.	

Denial of an analytical workflow

#: ujGdi12	Story name: Deny of an analytical workflow
	Triggered by User Role: Technical personal from national SPE
	Authors and Contributors: EGJ, CHF
<p>Preconditions</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">- The user authenticates themselves in GDI following ujGdi01.- The user has submitted an analytical workflow for validation. <p>Description</p> <p>The GDI validation committee receives a notification from GDI's Federation Commutation Dashboard indicating that an analytical workflow has been submitted for validations.</p> <p>The committee inspects the multiple tasks of the workflow to ensure no data is leaked during its execution and that all the operations performed are permeated in the project.</p> <p>If the committee identifies a possible data leak or that some of the operations performed by the analytical workflows are unacceptable within GDI's context, they flag the analytical workflow as rejected (indicating which operations are leaking data and/or which operations are not accepted).</p> <p>If the committee sees that all the tasks are correct, the committee then notifies the national nodes for local testing. The national nodes will be given a reasonable amount of time to locally test the workflow if desired.</p> <p>During that time the national nodes can test the analytical workflow. If they identify technical or legal issues that forbids them to run the workflow locally, they will document the issue and tag the workflow as unacceptable.</p> <p>Either because the validation committee flagged the analytical workflow as unacceptable or because some national node reported issues, the workflow is reported not to be accepted in GDI's system. In doing so, the GDI's Federated Computational Dashboard will notify the owner of the negative validation, providing useful feedback that can be used to fix the reported issues. The workflow then could be submitted again to GDI's network.</p> <p>Postconditions</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">- The analytical workflow was not included in GDI's system.- The user that submitted the workflow is notified of the negative results and useful feedback is provided in order to create a new analytical workflow with the same functionality but that has higher possibilities to be accepted in GDI.	

#: usGdi01.1	Story name: Enabling contact with treating healthcare professional for a patient diagnosed with metastatic melanoma		
	<table border="1"> <tr> <td data-bbox="597 323 1424 422">Triggered by User Role: Clinician/oncologist</td> </tr> <tr> <td data-bbox="597 422 1424 520">Authors and Contributors: From D7.5 - Cancer Research use case</td> </tr> </table>	Triggered by User Role: Clinician/oncologist	Authors and Contributors: From D7.5 - Cancer Research use case
Triggered by User Role: Clinician/oncologist			
Authors and Contributors: From D7.5 - Cancer Research use case			
<p>composed of genetic data (NGS sequencing of a melanoma treated with Vemurafenib, after developing resistance to the therapy) and the corresponding clinical data. Both raw genetic data (.Fastq file) and analysed data (.vcf file containing somatic mutations and BED file containing structural alterations) are present. Aggregated data could be visualised via a visualisation tool like in cBioportal.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • If needed, a communication channel with the relevant clinical contact related to the identified patient(s) can be set up. • The clinician applies for data access to 1+MG data (ujGdi04) and the Data Access Committee grants the access (ujGdi05). • The clinician downloads the genetic sequence data with the corresponding clinical data of the identified patient(s) (ujGdi09). <p>Postconditions: -</p>			

Cancer as a Rare Disease

#: usGdi03	Story name: Cancer as a Rare Disease
	Triggered by User Role: Clinician/oncologist Authors and Contributors: From D7.5 - Cancer Research use case

User story description:

A healthcare professional comes across an interesting case during one of their weekly Molecular Tumour Board (MTB) sessions at their institute. A pancreatic acinar cell carcinoma (PACC) patient is presented as having a complex histological pattern and an uncommon BRAF sequence alteration: V600_K601delinsE. The clinician wonders whether the patient can be treated as if he/she has a 'classical' BRAF V600E variant and searches for any other patients harbouring the non-canonical BRAF variant identified and treated at other European centres. This information would guide the decision-making process, suggesting the most suitable therapeutic choice(s) for the patient. Since the specific BRAF variant is rarely found in this kind of cancer patients, access to a broad cohort would be helpful. The clinician would like to know if any patients corresponding to this profile exist and, if so, to learn more about their clinical history, treatment and outcome.

The goal is to search for additional data in GDI to understand whether other patients with similar clinical/molecular characteristics carrying an unusual genetic alteration in the BRAF gene have been observed and possibly treated (and how) at other European nodes. The availability of a (small) cohort of similar patients with additional information regarding the administered therapy as well as patients' responses would guide the user to choose suitable therapeutic options.

As a clinician, I want to understand from a small cohort of similar patients how certain gene variants affect disease progression and/or response to treatment.

Preconditions:

The clinician must be authenticated and authorised to GDI.

Description:

- The clinician logs into the GDI platform ([ujGdi01](#)) and browses the available datasets ([ujGdi02](#) or [ujGdi03](#)).
- The user performs a Beacon query ([ujGdi03](#)) over the aggregate level data to get the presence of the BRAF variant (V600_K601delinsE) within the GDI infrastructure (focus on pancreatic cancer).
- The GDI user interface returns results, which includes datasets obtained from other patients with the same cancer type identified at multiple nodes of the network. The

Metastatic Colorectal Cancer

#: usGdi04	Story name: Metastatic Colorectal Cancer
	Triggered by User Role: Researcher
	Authors and Contributors: From D7.5 - Cancer Research use case

User story description:

A researcher aims to validate proposed gene signatures for the prognosis and survival of metastatic Colorectal Cancer (CRC) patients (ROS1, PIK3CA, LRP1B and FAT4) - that have not been fully confirmed in independent datasets. For this, the researcher aims to assemble retrospective cohorts from different data sources coming from different countries, including genomics and clinical data. The researcher has a pre-compiled pipeline relevant for the use case, to ensure that results are comparable.

The goal is to validate known gene signatures and discover new ones that are associated with CRC. Specifically, the aim is to identify how these gene signatures correlate with clinical factors such as tumour location, patient age and disease stage.

As a researcher, I want to validate the signature of specific genes as prognostic markers across multiple comparable population datasets.

Preconditions:

The researcher must be authenticated and authorised to GDI.

Description:

- The researcher logs into the GDI platform ([ujGdi01](#)) and browses available datasets ([ujGdi02](#) or [ujGdi03](#)).
- The researcher uses targeted search terms to filter the Central Data Catalogue ([ujGdi02](#)) such as colorectal cancer. Data are filtered to focus on the most relevant cases: CRC patients and with details concerning the patient characteristics, disease stage, diagnosis and perhaps treatment.
- The GDI returns results, which could include human genomic or genetic datasets annotated with CRC diagnosis and potentially other phenotypic information, found on one or multiple nodes of the network. We note that gene panels are more frequently applied in clinical settings.
- The researcher applies for data access to 1+MG data ([ujGdi04](#)) and the Data Access Committee grants the access ([ujGdi05](#)).
- The researcher accesses genetic sequence data for further analysis. The researcher executes the analysis by distributing an interoperable analysis pipeline across federated

GWAS analysis

#: usGdi05	Story name: GWAS analysis
	Triggered by User Role: Researcher
	Authors and Contributors: From D7.5 - Infectious diseases use case
<p>User story description: A researcher needs to query the GDI infrastructure and perform a rapid Genome-Wide Association Study (GWAS) in order to validate risk variants determining the severity of COVID-19. As GWAS requires large sample sizes, multiple comparable datasets are often needed.</p> <p>The goal is to find human genomic datasets that include patients with severe COVID-19. Performing a GWAS in a federated analysis scheme.</p> <p>As a researcher, I want to perform a GWAS across multiple comparable population datasets.</p> <p>Preconditions: The researcher must be authenticated and authorised to GDI</p> <p>Description:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The researcher logs into the GDI platform (ujGdi01). - The researcher needs to query and filter the Central Data Catalogue (ujGdi02) for both human genomic data (i.e. SNPs, variants) and phenotypic data associated with COVID-19 severity (i.e. hospitalisation, ICU admission, mortality). - The GDI returns results, which could include human genomic datasets annotated with Covid-19 severity indicators and potentially other phenotypic information, found on one or multiple nodes of the network. - The researcher applies for data access to 1+MG data (ujGdi04) and the Data Access Committee grants the access (ujGdi05). - The researcher accesses the annotated genetic sequence data for further analysis. The researcher executes the analysis by distributing an interoperable analysis pipeline across federated locations (ujGdi08). The researcher can add a workflow to the secure processing environment (SPE) (ujGdi10). - The researcher can download the results from his research results account for further processing (ujGdi09). 	

GWAS analyses across federated nodes

#: usGdi05.1	Story name: GWAS analyses across federated nodes
	Triggered by User Role: Researcher
	Authors and Contributors: From D7.5 - 1+MG/B1MG use case
<p>User story description: As a researcher, I want to perform a GWAS across multiple comparable population datasets. This is an extension of usGdi05.</p> <p>The goal is to identify genes associated with a particular disease or trait using provided whole genomes. The primary output of a GDI GWAS analysis is a list of P values, effect sizes and their directions generated from the association tests of all tested genetic variants with a phenotype of interest.</p> <p>Preconditions:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The researcher must be authenticated and authorised to GDI - Relevant disease or trait and WGS data must be available for cohort building (ujGdi02) <p>Description:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The researcher logs into the GDI platform (ujGdi01) - The researcher needs to define the study cohort using diseases or trait conditions (ujGdi03) - The GDI returns results, which include the list of human genomic datasets that have specified disease or traits. - The researcher applies for data access to 1+MG data (ujGdi04) and the Data Access Committee grants the access (ujGdi05). - If a researcher gets the approval, then the researcher can access genetic sequence data indirectly by using predefined GWAS pipelines. - The researcher executes the GWAS analysis by distributing GWAS pipelines to federated processing locations (ujGdi08 and ujGdi10). Individual participants' data stay within the country. - The researcher gets the relevant GWAS result data (like list of P values, Manhattan plots etc) to his research results account. - The researcher can download the results from his research results account for further processing (ujGdi09). 	

Annex

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Documentation

- Data request flow proposal: [Milestone 7 Coordination - V1.1](#)

Proposed GDI Access Workflow

Figure 1: Proposed GDI / 1+MG Data Access workflow